

Evaluating Tidal and Wave Corrections on Shoreline Extraction from Satellite Imagery in Mediterranean Microtidal Beaches

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Abstract—Accurate monitoring of shoreline variations is essential for effective coastal management and determining the consequent mitigation strategies, accounting for the critical effect of coastal erosion. Remote sensing technology has greatly enhanced the capability to analyze these dynamic environments, especially in the last years, thanks to the high resolutions of the recent sensing instruments. However, the accuracy of shoreline extraction methodologies can be influenced by natural phenomena such as tides and wave action, which can cause significant temporal variations in instantaneous shoreline positions. Therefore, incorporating tidal and wave corrections is crucial to refine these automated outputs. This study investigates the impact of tidal and wave corrections on a set of satellite-derived data from an automated tool. A comparison of shorelines derived from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope images is presented. The results demonstrate high accuracy, with a mean absolute error ranging from 2 to 4 meters, across three tideless Mediterranean beaches. Tidal and wave corrections did not significantly impact the accuracy of the results. Due to the augmented reliability of the extracted shorelines, further detailed analyses will highlight the role of this correction in multitemporal images.

Index Terms—Coastal erosion, PlanetScope, Remote sensing, Sentinel-2, Shoreline extraction, Tidal corrections, Wave corrections

I. INTRODUCTION

Coastal areas are vital to both natural ecosystems and human societies, serving as hubs of biodiversity, economic activity, and cultural heritage. These regions support diverse habitats, provide resources for fishing and tourism industries, and protect inland areas from storm surges and erosion. However, coastal areas are increasingly threatened by the erosion

process, which intensifies due to the impact of climate change, sea level rise, and human activities such as construction and land reclamation [1]. Accurate monitoring of coastal area changes is essential for effective management, which can help safeguard these areas from further degradation [2].

The most commonly used indicator for coastal environment monitoring is the shoreline position, defined as the water-land boundary line [3]. Traditional methods for shoreline monitoring, such as field surveys and aerial photogrammetry, provide valuable data but are often constrained by high costs, limited spatial coverage, and temporal infrequency [4]. Recent advancements in remote sensing technologies have significantly enhanced our ability to monitor coastal changes with greater accuracy and efficiency [5].

Satellite imagery has emerged as a powerful tool due to its wide spatial coverage and frequent revisit times. Sentinel-2 (S2), part of the European Space Agency's Copernicus program, has been widely utilized for coastal studies due to its medium spatial resolution (10 meters) and five-day revisit cycle. Previous studies have already demonstrated the utility of S2 in detecting shoreline changes and mapping coastal features, allowing for the differentiation of land and water boundaries, essential for accurate shoreline extraction [6].

PlanetScope (PS) constellation of small satellites provides even higher temporal resolution with its daily imagery which is particularly beneficial for monitoring dynamic coastal environments where rapid changes can occur. For example, the study by Abdelhady et al. [7] showed that Planet's high-frequency data can improve the detection of short-term shoreline variations and provide more timely information for coastal management.

However, the accuracy of shoreline extraction is influenced by natural phenomena such as tides and wave action, which can cause significant temporal variations in shoreline positions [8], [9]. These factors can lead to discrepancies in shoreline data if not properly accounted resulting in misleading interpretations of coastal changes. Therefore, incorporating tidal and wave corrections can be fundamental for refining these automated outputs, ensuring that the extracted shorelines reflect as much as possible the true position.

Finally, the validation of the extracted shorelines constitutes an important step of this research: the use of certified orthophotos as validation data ensures that the obtained results are grounded in reliable and accurate reference data. Such orthoimagery is in fact characterized by both high spatial resolution and georeferencing accuracy, so it can be reliably set as benchmark for assessing the accuracy of the satellite-derived shorelines.

This paper aims at (i) evaluating the impact of tidal and wave corrections on the accuracy of the shoreline extracted through the automated tool presented in [10], and (ii) providing additional evidence of the effectiveness of the methodology proposed in the same study, extending the validation to a temporally larger dataset of the same tideless Mediterranean beaches.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents a brief overview of the state of the art on the topic, including some of the most commonly used tools for shoreline extraction. Section III describes the dataset and the performed experiments, with some preliminary results presented in Section IV. Section V analyzes the findings. Finally, considerations and future improvements are reported in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several automated shoreline extraction tools have been developed to process satellite imagery and delineate shoreline positions [11]. These tools leverage various image processing techniques, including edge detection, classification algorithms, and machine learning approaches.

One of the key challenges in shoreline extraction is the influence of tidal and wave conditions, as their variations can cause significant temporal shifts in the *instantaneous* shoreline position. Methods to correct for wave influences, such as those proposed by [12], involve integrating wave data to calculate the run-up to adjust the shoreline positions.

The comparison of different shoreline extraction methods reported in [11] highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of each technique, emphasizing the need for method selection based on specific coastal conditions and research objectives. Such analysis also examined the performance of various tools (e.g., SHOREX, CASSIE, CoastSat) and compared them with those obtained with the wave/tidal corrections derived from the Stockdon's formula [12] and offshore data from the nearest beach point in the ERA5 model [11].

Recent studies evaluated shoreline detection systems at high-energy mesotidal beaches and found that correcting for wave setup/runup can enhance the accuracy and precision

of time-series data. For instance, the CoastSat time-series of Ocean Beach (San Francisco) was improved by applying a slope-independent wave setup parametrization [13]. Similarly, a wave runup parametrization [14] was applied to SHOREX SDS time-series of the Faro beach (Portugal), and a different slope-independent wave setup formulation [15] was used for Truc Vert (France). These studies indicate that there is no one-size-fits-all solution and that further research is still necessary to determine the optimal wave corrections application across different coastal environments and beach morphologies.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study areas

This study was conducted on three sandy tideless coastlines within the Mediterranean: the beach of Castelldefels (CDF) and Gavà in Spain (top of Fig. 1), and the Feniglia (FNG) and the Marina di Grosseto (MRN) beaches in Tuscany, Italy (bottom of Fig. 1). These locations, being part of the Mediterranean basin, feature minimal tidal oscillations and predominantly calm wave conditions with occasional storms. Some details on the three case studies are provided below.

The CDF beach area is semi-urban, extends over 10 km, and consists of fine sediments from the Llobregat River; it experiences predominant waves from East, South-East [16].

The FNG beach is a 6 km embayment forming one of the two spits of the Orbetello Lagoon. It faces direct exposure to waves from the SE, S, and SW, with the first two impacting the entire coast while the SW waves significantly affect only the eastern stretch due to the presence of the Monte Argentario, which partially protects the western side.

The MRN beach segment spans 4.5 km northward from the urban area, with the Ombrone River Delta experiencing significant erosion [17]. In this case, the dominant sea currents mainly come from the South-West.

B. Datasets

S2 imagery includes thirteen bands, ranging from visible to shortwave infrared, with four bands at 10 m spatial resolution (blue, green, red, and near-infrared), six bands at 20 m, and three bands at 60 m for atmospheric corrections. Each S2 satellite covers a swath width of 290 km [18]. PS imagery has a spatial resolution of 3 m, which means a higher level of detail if compared to the S2. Moreover, they guarantee a swath width of approximately 24 km. This allows for near-real-time monitoring of dynamic changes in coastal areas and other environments. Since 2017, PS has provided at least four spectral bands (blue, green, red, and near-infrared), similar to the core visible and NIR bands of S2 [19].

The dataset used in this study consists of three S2 and three PS images, one for each site; S2 level-2A (L2A) products, orthorectified and georeferenced, have been selected, while PS images are provided already orthorectified, georeferenced, and radiometrically adjusted to S2 bands. The images for CDF sites were georeferenced in UTM 31N while the images for FNG and MRN share the UTM 32N reference system. The

Fig. 1. Study areas: a section of Llobregat Delta in front of Castelfelers (CDF) (Spain) in 1), the beaches of Marina di Grosseto (MRN) (Italy) and Feniglia (FNG) (Italy) in 2).

images were selected as close as possible to the dates of the reference orthomosaics (Table I).

A Digital Surface Model (DSM) with a 1 m grid, distributed by the Tuscany Region was used to assess the necessary altimetric information and the slope of the MRN beach, choosing the same frames as the respective orthomosaic. For the Feniglia beach, a LiDAR survey made by the authors was employed. It provides a 30 cm DSM grid. However, for the CDF beach, LiDAR data were downloaded from the Geoportal de Cartografia of the AMB (Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona) and provided a 1 m grid.

As relates to the sea-level data, they were sourced from the Barcelona harbor tide gauge for the CDF coast, Civitavecchia harbor for the FNG beach, and Marina di Campo harbor for the MRN coast. Wave conditions were instead obtained from the Barcelona Buoy II (Puertos del Estado, Spain) for the CDF coast, Giannutri buoy (Servizio Idrologico Regionale, Tuscany region, Italy) for the FNG beach, and Castiglione della Pescaia buoy (Servizio Idrologico Regionale, Tuscany region, Italy) for the MRN coastal stretch.

Finally, three orthomosaics were used for reference and validation. The first one was obtained from the Institut Cartogràfic

i Geològic de Catalunya: it is available in three bands and has a spatial resolution of 25 cm. The second was realized through the data acquired during the LiDAR survey campaign at the Feniglia beach. It provides a spatial resolution of 10 cm. The third orthomosaic, covering the MRN beach, is provided by the Tuscany Region through the GEOscopio WMS (Web Map Service) portal. This product includes four bands: Near-Infrared (NIR), Red, Green, and Blue, with a spatial resolution of 20 cm.

TABLE I
DATES OF REFERENCE ORTHOMOSAICS, TEMPORAL DISCREPANCY (IN DAYS) OF S2 AND PS IMAGERY FROM REFERENCE DATA.

Site	Reference Date	S2 diff. (days)	PS diff. (days)
CDF	25/05/2017	2	2
FNG	05/04/2023	2	1
MRN	20/07/2019	4	0

C. Methodology

This work is based on the shoreline extraction methodology developed in [10], extended in order to provide planimetric correction of tidal and wave run-up contributions. The tool is developed in Python, and the QGIS software was also used for additional graphical outputs and validation. Such methodology foresees an initial preprocessing phase of satellite imagery by calculating various spectral indices (NDWI, MNDWI, WI, AWEIshadow, and AWEI no-shadow for S2 and NDWI and NIR band for PS). Two unsupervised classifications, the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) and K-means, are then run to binarize the rasters into water and land and extract the contours. The water levels and the waves at both satellite time and shoreline reference time were used to calculate the difference using Stockdon's formula [12] (1):

$$z_{\text{runup}} = 0.35 \cdot \tan(\beta) \cdot \sqrt{H_s \cdot L_0} \quad (1)$$

where H_s is the significant wave height, L_0 is the deep-water wavelength, and β is the beach slope.

L_0 is defined as:

$$L_0 = \frac{g \cdot T^2}{2\pi} \quad (2)$$

where T represents the wave period.

The beach slopes were calculated for each beach considering only the swash zone using DSM data. The obtained values are 0.061 rad for MRN, 0.071 rad for FNG, and 0.078 rad for CDF.

The difference between the reference shorelines and those extracted from the satellite data was calculated to adjust the latter to the time of the reference ones. The two components of displacement given by the tide and by the wave run-up were calculated using (3) and (4) respectively and then added to obtain the final displacement.

$$d_{\text{tide}} = \frac{z_{\text{tide-sat}} - z_{\text{tide-ref}}}{\tan(\beta)} \quad (3)$$

where d_{tide} is the displacement given by the tidal contribution, with $z_{\text{tide-sat}}$ representing the tide at satellite time and $z_{\text{tide-ref}}$ the tide at reference time.

$$d_{\text{runup}} = \frac{z_{\text{runup-sat}} - z_{\text{runup-ref}}}{\tan(\beta)} \quad (4)$$

where d_{runup} is the displacement given by the runup contribution, with $z_{\text{runup-sat}}$ being the runup at satellite time and $z_{\text{runup-ref}}$ the runup at reference time.

To finally correct the extracted shorelines we used the same transects from the validation phase. The original shorelines were sampled every meter, and the points were shifted towards the baseline: a negative displacement value means landward movement and a positive value means seaward shift. The connecting line across the new points needed to be smoothed at the same level as the raw shorelines.

The accuracy of S2 and PS-derived shorelines, both before and after correction, was evaluated by comparing them with the reference shorelines obtained through a manual digitalization from high-resolution aerial orthomosaics. The comparison involved computing various metrics using cross-shore transects spaced at 10-meter intervals. This systematic approach is known as ‘‘baseline and transect’’ [20].

IV. RESULTS

The calculation of the total displacement value, given by the sum of the tidal and run-up contributions, yielded values exceeding one meter in four out of six cases (Table II). All values were positive, indicating a landward displacement of the satellite-extracted shorelines. A displacement of 1.4 m was observed for the PS data on the CDF beach, while for the FNG beach, a 1.5 m shift and 1.3 m shift were observed for the S2 and the PS data respectively. A displacement of 1.5 m was observed for the PS data on the MRN coast.

TABLE II
DATE OF REFERENCE ORTHOMOSAICS AND TOTAL DISPLACEMENT BETWEEN S2 AND PS DATA AND REFERENCE SHORELINE.

Site	Reference Date	Total distance (m)	
		S2 - Reference	PS - Reference
CDF	25/05/2017	0.4	1.4
FNG	05/04/2023	1.5	1.3
MRN	20/07/2019	0.3	1.5

Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Bias, and Root Mean Square (RMS) of the shoreline position error for each case study are reported in Table III. All possible combinations were tested but only the best combination method-index is shown in the two versions, without correction (raw) and with the total contribution of tidal and run-up corrections (transl) (Table III).

The results show a high level of accuracy for both versions. Fig. 2 shows a visual example of the obtained results. S2 data exhibit an accuracy of approximately one-third of a pixel in terms of MAD for CDF (≤ 2 m) and FNG (≤ 3.5 m), and around half a pixel for MRN (≈ 5 m). The PS results show slightly lower accuracy in terms of MAD but still lower than the pixel size. In general, the best results are obtained for the beaches of CDF and FNG (~ 2 m). In most of the cases tidal and run-up corrections led to changes, usually reductions, of the error at decimeter level.

Fig. 2. Visually results of FNG beach: a) show a general view and a zoom of the best method-index combination for S2 data, b) show a general view and a zoom of the best method-index combination for PS data.

TABLE III
STATISTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SHORELINE POSITION ERROR: RESULTS ARE REPORTED FOR THE BEST METHODOLOGIES (INDEX AND METHOD) FOR EACH DATE AND SITE, DISTINGUISHING ORIGINAL (RAW) SHORELINES AND THOSE WITH TIDAL AND WAVE CORRECTIONS (TRANSL).

Site	Type	Index	Method	MAD (m)	Bias (m)	RMS (m)
Sentinel-2						
CDF	raw	NDWI	GMM	1.9	-0.9	2.5
	transl	NDWI	GMM	1.8	-0.5	2.4
FNG	raw	MNDWI	K-means	3.2	0.2	4.2
	transl	MNDWI	K-means	3.5	1.7	4.5
MRN	raw	AWEIsh	K-means	5.1	-1.9	6.1
	transl	AWEIsh	K-means	4.9	-1.4	5.9
PlanetScope						
CDF	raw	NIR	K-means	1.3	-0.7	1.7
	transl	NIR	K-means	1.9	1.5	2.9
FNG	raw	NIR	K-means	2.0	-1.4	2.4
	transl	NIR	K-means	1.7	-0.1	2.0
MRN	raw	NDWI	GMM	2.4	-1.0	2.8
	transl	NDWI	GMM	2.1	0.4	2.4

V. DISCUSSION

The obtained results are in line with the previous study conducted for the same sites but on different dates [10]. The same pattern emerges with the best performance observed for the beaches of CDF and FNG and the worst performance for the MRN. This coastal stretch represents a more complex environment, where it will be necessary in the future to implement differentiated strategies for different sections of the beach with varying contexts. As specifically relates the PS data, the best performance was achieved in two out of the three sites using the same index-method combination (NIR-K-means). For the S2 data, it was not possible to define a one index method fitting different beaches. This suggests that it is not possible to establish the same index-method combination in every case, in line with the conclusions drawn in previous studies [21]. Similar considerations apply to the accuracy as well [11].

Tidal and wave correction resulted in changes in the computed error statistics at the decimeter level, often, but not always, leading to a slight error reduction, in agreement with the findings of other works [11]. The need to analyze other site-specific sources of error related to morphological characteristics at the beach level or to the coregistration of satellite images is clear.

In this work, a simplified version of Stockdon's formula [12] was used to calculate the run-up. Future developments will focus on adapting the formula to different morphological contexts (dissipative beaches) and various wave conditions. Another possible implementation may include the use of synthetic data when in-situ data from buoys and tide gauges are too distant. Current models allow for resolutions up to 200 m along the coast and exhibit a bias of approximately 0.5 m compared to in situ data [22].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates the effect of integrating tidal and wave corrections into the shoreline extraction process from satellite imagery to enhance its reliability.

The use of high-resolution satellite imagery from S2 and PS offers substantial benefits for coastal monitoring: in fact, their combination allows for a comprehensive and timely data elaboration which is essential for capturing the dynamic nature of shorelines. Moreover, automated shoreline extraction tools need some refinement to consider effects such as tidal and wave actions that can cause temporal variations in shoreline positions. In this context, this study demonstrates that the integration of Stockdon's formula in the shoreline extraction process generates more robust results, thus helping in the normalization of the shoreline positions.

Further improvement will focus on validating the results using multi-temporal high-resolution orthomosaics and extracted shorelines to further verify the correlation after computing their linear regression rate. This will allow for the quantification of the improvements achieved through the correction methods.

Future research will continue to explore the integration of various data sources and correction techniques to further refine current shoreline extraction methods. Additionally, the application of these methodologies to diverse coastal environments will help validate their generalizability and effectiveness, contributing to global efforts in coastal preservation and management.

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